

Shepherding Movement

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The Shepherding Movement, aka Christian Growth Movement, was a sub movement within the larger Charismatic Movement during the 1970s and 1980s. It was founded by a group of US pastors dubbed the "Fort Lauderdale Five:" Don Basham, Bob Mumford, Derek Prince, Charles Simpson, and Ern Baxter. Believing that current churches and pastors were losing sight of the value of discipleship and were caving to worldly practices and cultures, the movement emphasized personal accountability and mentorship where adherents would submit themselves to a "shepherd." Leaders in the movement required participants to attend additional life group meetings, usually in someone's home, and to have shepherds, leaders, and elders approve all life decisions, including but not limited to: marriage, where to live, taking a new job or leaving a current job, or going to the doctor if ill. As the Shepherding Movement expanded throughout the United States, networks of communities began to emerge in the shape of a pyramid structure. The networks would meet locally in cell churches. Shepherds would have multiple disciples under them, and those shepherds would be under the authority of shepherds above them. These relationships became known as "covenant relationships" and the disciple was required to submit in all areas of life and tithe directly to the shepherd who would move the money up the authoritative structure. Leaders in the Pentecostal and Charismatic communities began to scrutinize the Shepherding Movement as the movement continued to grow and gain influence. Concerns about tithing to shepherds and the rigid structures of submission and of the covenant relationships were articulated by various pastors throughout the nation. Nationally recognized leaders such as Pat Robertson, Kathryn Khulman, and Demos Shakarian denounced the movement and distanced themselves from the founding leaders. By the 1980s, the movement began to fracture as the unity of the leaders disintegrated. Derek Prince and Bob Mumford publicly disassociated from the movement. In 1983, Derek Prince stated that the movement was an error. Bob Mumford publicly asked for forgiveness for his role in the movement in 1989. The movement waned during the 1990s and into the early 2000s as more adherents left the movement citing abuses from leadership. Due to the breakup of the founding leaders, there is little information as to how many adherents remain.

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2000 CE

Region: United States of America .

Region tags: United States

United States of America

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology by S. David Moore
- Source 2: World Christian Encyclopedia ed. David Barrett

– Source 3: *Damaged Disciples: Casualties of Authoritarian Churches and the Shepherding Movement* by Ron Burks

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YsLRW49hCx0>
- Source 1 Description: An interview with one of the founders, Derek Prince. Prince shares about the mistakes with the Shepherding Movement
- Source 2 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FeBJMk_ycNk
- Source 2 Description: A continuation of the interview with Derek Prince. Prince explains about the rationale behind the founding of the Shepherding Movement.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.christianitytoday.com/ct/1990/march-19/shepherding-movement-idea-whose-time-has-gone.html>
- Source 1 Description: A brief history and reflection of the Shepherding Movement from Christianity Today in 1990

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://csmpublishing.org/publications/new-wine-magazine/>
- Source 1 Description: These are online archived scans of New Wine Magazine. New Wine Magazine was a publication for adherents of the Shepherding Movement.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: As an outgrowth of the Charismatic movement of the 1970s, the Shepherding Movement was founded and expanded by separating out of existing congregations.

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Century of the Holy Spirit*. Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson, 2000.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: The identifying marker of participation in the Shepherding Movement is submitting to a shepherd. It was up to shepherds to find new individuals and families to shepherd and lead.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

Reference: Basham, Don. *True and False Prophets: Confronting Immorality in Ministry*. Grand Rapids: Chosen Books, 1994.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– No

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Reference: Burks, Ron, and Vicki Burks. *Damaged Disciples: Casualties of Authoritarian Churches and the Shepherding Movement*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1992.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– Yes

↳ Other divine punishment:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 100000

Notes: This data is from the World Christian Encyclopedia.

Reference: David, Barrett, ed.. World Christian Encyclopedia. Edited by Barrett David. New York: Oxford University Press, 1982.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region)

population, numerical):

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement used the Protestant Bible that contains the Old and New Testaments.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement uses the Protestant Old Testament and New Testament as the sacred texts.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of the Shepherding Movement believe that the biblical texts of the Old and New Testaments are inspired by God and were canonized with the direction of the Holy Spirit.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of the Shepherding Movement believed that parts of the biblical texts were revealed by God including the Ten Commandments and other laws in the Old Testament.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement believes that the Old and New Testaments are God-breathed or inspired by God as stated in 1 Timothy 3:16-17.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:
– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:
– Yes

Notes: The four canonical gospels are believed to preserve the teachings of Jesus Christ who is believed to be fully God and fully human.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:
– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement believes that the canonical biblical texts were produced by non-divine humans that were inspired by God.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:
– Yes

Notes: Recognized pastors and leaders in the movement are trained in transmitting the scriptures. Although lay people are permitted to read the scriptures, their interpretation of them must align with the leadership of the movement for the interpretation to be deemed appropriate.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:
– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement adheres to the Protestant Canon with the Old Testament and New Testament.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:
– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement is part of the larger Charismatic Movement that emerged during the mid-twentieth century in the United States. The movement held to theological beliefs consistent with participants of the Charismatic Movement. Since the Charismatic Movement encompassed numerous denominations and non-denominational congregations, there may be some who believe that humans consist of mind, body, and spirit, while others may hold to a body and soul distinction. Irregardless of the position, there is a clear distinction between the body and some conception of the spirit.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008. https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Much like other aspects of theology among Charismatics, their particular theology on the human spirit and soul rests on the specific denomination they identify with. However, there is a common belief among them that there are non-physical aspects of a person's anthropology. They believe that when a person dies, their spirit and/or soul is separated from the body but is reunited with the body during the resurrection at the end of time.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe in an afterlife for all people, contingent upon their acceptance of God's salvation through Jesus Christ. According to Charismatic theology, only those who acknowledge Jesus Christ as their Lord and Savior will enjoy eternal communion with God. This doctrine firmly interconnects the concepts of the afterlife and soteriology, as it asserts that all humans are sinners due to the account of humanity's fall in Genesis 3. Through the atoning death and subsequent resurrection of Jesus Christ, those who openly confess their faith in Him are destined for an eternity in God's presence following their earthly passage. In Charismatic traditions, it is held that the saved will be welcomed into the heavenly presence of Jesus Christ upon their earthly departure, whereas those who have not embraced salvation are expected to face damnation in Hell. Among Charismatic Renewalists, who maintain various degrees of adherence to their primary denominational or non-denominational beliefs regarding the afterlife, a range of viewpoints can be found. While some Charismatic Renewalists align with the Charismatic perspective, others may hold divergent views. Charismatic theology further links the afterlife with eschatology, asserting that after the return of Jesus Christ to Earth and the ultimate defeat of evil, there will be a resurrection of all deceased individuals. During this event, both their spirit and body will be reunited. The saved will receive a glorified body, securing their eternal fellowship with God, while those who remain unsaved will be condemned to the eternal torment of the Lake of Fire.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008. https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Views about the afterlife within the Shepherding Movement are dependent upon the mainline denomination they belong to. However, despite theological differences about eschatology and soteriology, there is a common thread that some people will live with God for eternity, and others will spend eternity apart from God.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics and the Shepherding Movement believe that a person is conscious after death. Those who follow Jesus Christ are with him and those who do not follow Jesus Christ are believed to be present in hell. There is also a belief based on the book of Revelation that God will usher in a new heaven and a new earth where followers of Jesus will reside after the resurrection. Those who are not followers of Jesus will be judged and thrown in the lake of fire.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Funerals and memorial services are important rituals for adherents of the Shepherding Movement. The liturgy of the funeral or memorial service may have differences amongst denominations and movements that identify as part of the Charismatic movement. No matter the liturgical differences, each denomination and group has some formal ritual for honoring the deceased.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Charismatics believe in supernatural beings, both good and evil. There is a belief in God, angels, cherubim, and seraphim as well as evil supernatural beings identified as Satan and demons. The way that people interact with these supernatural beings differs due to the different denominational theologies regarding these beings. Adherents of the Shepherding Movement believed the Baptism of the Holy Spirit as a subsequent experience to salvation. In addition, believers are taught to engage in spiritual warfare with evil spirits. Those who are baptized in the Holy Spirit are able to provide physical and spiritual healing as well as perform various forms of miracles.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMjF3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Livingston, James C.. *Anatomy of the Sacred*. Prentice Hall, 2008.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Anatomy_of_the_Sacred.html?hl=&id=5pCNHwaACAAJ.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Participants of the Shepherding Movement believe in trinitarian monotheism where God is the Father, Son, and Holy Spirit.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement believes that Jesus Christ is God incarnate. Jesus is both fully God and fully human. See Rev. Derek Prince preach on "Put All Things Under the Feet of Jesus" - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yJ9Z6WBvMyc>

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Charismatic Christians, adherents of the Shepherding Movement believed that God is supremely good. Here is a short teaching about God's goodness from Derek Prince: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y_OeduuRjpY

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Trinitarian Monotheism

Notes: Participants of the Shepherding Movement believe in Trinitarian Monotheism. They believe in a monotheistic God who consists of the Father, Jesus Christ, and the Holy Spirit. Each person of the Trinity is distinct from one another but also fully God. There are some variations in the theology of the Trinity between different Charismatic within mainline Protestant denominations but they all believe in Trinitarian Monotheism.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

Reference: Synan, Vinson. *The Holiness-pentecostal Tradition*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1997. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Q-npoRWoZuUC>.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Charismatic Christians, adherents of the Shepherding Movement believed that God has knowledge of the United States, and they believed God wanted his followers to expand their influence throughout the nation. Civic leaders have a responsibility to God since God appointed them in the positions in the first place.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes

Notes: Here is a sermon from Derek Prince on God's dealings with the hearts of people: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=95tNmgsA1C4>

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

Reference: Bowler, Kate. *Blessed*. Oxford University Press, 2018.
<https://books.google.com/books/about/Blessed.html?hl=&id=oJc4DwAAQBAJ>.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Here is a series of teachings from Derek Prince on hearing the voice of God:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZB-nC9jWuhM&list=PL_L1za0tEXFUpJajtSOE46EMjiHKsGary

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: As part of the larger Charismatic Movement, adherents of the Shepherding Movement believe that God speaks to people through words of knowledge, prophetic words, and through other mediums such as dreams or visions.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Participants of the Shepherding Movement believed that God could speak to them through dreams. All participants needed to share their visions and dreams to their shepherd for accountability.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: S. David Moore explains the logic of the founders of the Shepherding Movement and states, "Their analysis of the condition of the Charismatic Renewal and broader Christianity is especially important to understanding the Shepherding movement's self-concept. They saw themselves seeking to be 'men of Issachar, who understood the times and knew what Israel should do' (1 Chron. 12.30 NIV). They felt they were perceiving the issues facing the church and giving leadership in response to prophetic insight. Bob Mumford often referred to what he called a 'now word' or a 'preceding word'. His idea was that God was speaking contemporaneously to his people to give them guidance by emphasizing certain essential truths or teachings. The teachings that were to become their trademark on authority, submission, discipleship, Shepherding care, and the kingdom of God were seen as 'living-edge truths' to confront and guide their generation." Moore, S. David, *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology* (T & T Clark International: New York, 2004), p. 44.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Prophecy

Notes: Adherents of the movement were instructed to clarify all prophetic insights with their shepherd.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The founders, particularly Derek Prince, were very interested in spiritual beings and spiritual warfare. Prince would often teach about demonology and he believed that the Shepherding Movement would deliver people from various forms of spiritual bondage.

Reference: Bowler, Kate. *Blessed*. Oxford University Press, 2018.

<https://books.google.com/books/about/Blessed.html?hl=&id=oJc4DwAAQBAJ>.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: There is a belief in supernatural beings such as angels, demons, cherubim, and seraphim.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: There is a belief that spiritual beings can interact with humans. In addition, there is belief that humans can be influenced or possessed by demons.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed that non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of the world but do not have foreknowledge of what will take place in the future.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Non-human beings are restricted to their knowledge of the domains and realms that God gives them.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden

motives):

– No

Notes: Like other Charismatics, adherents of the Shepherding Movement believe that only God can see into the hearts and minds of humans.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Charismatic traditions, The Shepherding Movement, believes that evil spirits such as demons can affect and influence people who are believed to be living in sin. It is not directly tied to reward and punishment but rather an adherent can open themselves up to the influences of demonic activity in their lives.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Evangelical and Charismatic movements, The Shepherding Movement believes that there are hierarchies of angelic beings such as angels and archangels.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement, like other Charismatic movements, believes that God has given over the earth to the domain of Satan and his demons.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian traditions, The Shepherding Movement believes that God watches what people do.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Homosexuality

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Honoring oaths or covenants is a hallmark of the Shepherding Movement. Adherents were to submit themselves to leaders of the movement in all aspects of their lives. S. David Moore explains, "They saw covenant relationship as the solid ground for permanent and stability within a disintegrating culture. A believer's relationship to God was firmly rooted in God's covenant love, demonstrated by Christ's sacrificial death. Consequently, believers were to commit themselves with the same kind of self-sacrificial love and loyalty to their leaders and fellow believers" (Moore, 76). God believes that his followers are to uphold their loyalty to him

and this is to be demonstrated by a followers' loyalty to their leaders.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Reference: Bowler, Kate. *Blessed*. Oxford University Press, 2018.
<https://books.google.com/books/about/Blessed.html?hl=&id=oJc4DwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness¹:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Christian traditions, The Shepherding Movement believes that Jesus Christ is the messiah. As God's son, Jesus' death and resurrection forgives sins and gives eternal life to those who follow him.

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of the Shepherding Movement believe that Jesus rose from the dead and is currently at the right hand of God.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: It's more about possibly in this lifetime rather than a certainty. Adherents of the Shepherding Movement believed that Jesus could return at any time and it is necessary for the believer to be ready for his return.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly, but there was no known date of Jesus Christ's return among adherents.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Coming has already passed:

– Yes

Notes: The New Testament in the Bible records Jesus Christ's activities during his first coming. His second coming has yet to come and adherents of the Shepherding Movement waited with anticipation.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: There was belief among some adherents of the Shepherding Movement that Jesus is a king who will return and rule God's creation.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: There is a belief that the return of Jesus Christ will bring about worship from all his followers.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The founders held to a now and not yet perception of the Kingdom of God. The Kingdom of God was ushered in during the life and ministry of Jesus Christ and is present throughout up to the present day. However, the Kingdom of God has not yet reach fulfillment. The culmination and fulfillment of the Kingdom of God on Earth will take place when Jesus Christ returns during his second coming. The founders of the Shepherding Movement believed that God was doing something unique with the Kingdom of God and that they were charged to bring about a restoration movement within Christianity to better align the church with God's Kingdom.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement adhered to Kingdom of God theology, which believed that the Kingdom of God was currently present but not fully realized. As time moves forward, the Kingdom of God is moving to it's ultimate culmination with the second coming of Jesus Christ.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement adhered to Kingdom of God theology, which believed that the Kingdom of God was currently present but not fully realized. As time moves forward, the Kingdom of God is moving to it's ultimate culmination with the second coming of Jesus Christ.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The leaders and adherents of the Shepherding Movement believed in two judgments: The Bema Seat Judgement and the White Throne Judgement. The Bema Seat Judgement was for believers in Jesus Christ and their lives would be judged according to how they served God. The White Throne Judgement is for non-believers and their judgement results in their eternal

torment in the lake of fire according to the book of Revelation.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: The leaders and adherents of the Shepherding Movement believed in a New Heaven and New Earth being ushered in at the end of time as per the prophecies at the conclusion of the book of Revelation.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Those who have confessed that Jesus Christ is their lord and savior will be saved. Only God knows who will be saved.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Reference: Duffield, Guy P., and Nathaniel M. Van Cleave. *Foundations of Pentecostal Theology*. Creation House, 2008. https://books.google.com/books/about/Foundations_of_Pentecostal_Theology.html?hl=&id=_EPTPAAACAAJ.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Moral norms are linked to the God of the Bible. Leaders and adherents believed that the Bible is God's literal word and prescribes the moral and ethical teachings of God.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: The moral commands of God in the Old Testament and the commands of Jesus in the New Testament were believed to be the supreme moral authority.

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
 - No

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - All individuals within society
 - All individuals within contemporary world
 - All individuals (any time period)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Adherents were to remain celibate if they were not married and were to report to their shepherd or leaders if they were not adhering to celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Reference: Williams, J. Rodman. *Renewal Theology*. Zondervan, 2011.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=wMJf3RITnNkC>.

- ↳ Monogamy (males):
 - Yes

- ↳ Monogamy (females):
 - Yes

- ↳ Other sexual constraints (males):
 - Yes

Notes: Sexual acts committed with anyone other than a female spouse were not permitted and were to be reported to the shepherd or other leaders.

- ↳ Other sexual constraints (females):
 - Yes

Notes: Sexual acts committed with anyone other than a male spouse were not permitted and were to be reported to the shepherd or other leaders.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Similar to other Charismatic groups in the US, adherents of the Shepherding Movement practiced fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents were required to tithe money to their shepherd. Shepherds were in charge of at least five to 10 individuals or family units. Each of these individuals for families would tithe to the shepherd. In turn, the shepherd would also submit to a shepherd above them and tithe directly to them.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The Shepherding Movement emphasized the concept of community and participation in house churches or cell groups was mandatory. Moore writes, "A believer was encouraged to find fatherhood in his or her shepherd. It taught that other lateral relationships with fellow believers in the house church or cell group resulted from the relationship a disciple made with the shepherd or spiritual father. In other words, the primary connection with the group was first to the shepherd, and spiritual family was a by-product." Gatherings were focused on devotion to the leader and lateral relationships were a by-product of submission to leadership. S. David Moore, *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology* (T & T Clark International: New York, 2003), 78.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The origins of the movement were rooted in a belief that churches and leaders were too loose with ethical precepts. S. David Moore explains, "Recognizing a need for guidelines to help mediate future disputes within the renewal, a 'code of ethics' was drawn up at the 1971 Seattle meeting. The 'document, entitled "Ethics for Christian Leaders", was drafted and solemnly agreed upon, although there was no formal signing of the document'. The document called for criticisms and complaints against any fellow leader or his ministry to be handled according to the Matthew 18 guidelines, by first

going privately to the person 'to establish the true facts'..." (Moore, 49). S. David Moore, *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology* (T & T Clark International: New York, 2003), 49.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents were required to build strong relationships with their leading shepherd and then build relationships with other believers in the cell group. They taught that anyone who was outside of the movement was missing God. S. David Moore, *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology* (T & T Clark International: New York, 2003), 148.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Adherents participated in house churches and rituals such as communion were taken in the home.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The best term to describe the Shepherding Movement is network.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Formal education in the form of schools or seminaries was frowned upon. Moore explains how Derek Prince, "stated that he did not recommend that people go to seminary, but instead advocated a mentoring model for ministry training... He taught that the elders of the local church are ultimately the final authority in local church affairs and that apostolic ministry must be invited in by the local presbytery of elders" (Moore, 63).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The structure of the movement was in the shape of a pyramid with the five founders at the top. Each of the founders had groups of individuals or families that they shepherded. In turn, each of those individuals had people under them. Adherents were required to be accountable to a shepherd and were required to participate in group functions of the cell churches.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

Reference: Burks, Ron, and Vicki Burks. *Damaged Disciples: Casualties of Authoritarian Churches and the Shepherding Movement*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1992.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents were required to tithe directly to their shepherd. According S. David Moore, it was believed that at least ten tithing households could support a shepherd who held a job in addition to leading a cell group (Moore, 80). Adherents of the movement were confronted if they did not tithe. S. David Moore, *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology* (T & T International: New York, 2003), 80.

Reference: Moore, S. David. *The Shepherding Movement: Controversy and Charismatic Ecclesiology*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2003.

Reference: Burks, Ron, and Vicki Burks. *Damaged Disciples: Casualties of Authoritarian Churches and the Shepherding Movement*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1992.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents still have to abide by the local, state, and federal laws. It was taught that God appointed government leaders and it was necessary to submit oneself to those in authority.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are permitted to serve in the armed forces.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents were subject to the authority of the US government and military.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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<https://books.google.com/books/about/Blessed.html?hl=&id=oJc4DwAAQBAJ> . . .

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